

Fabrication of Loofah Sponge as an Effective Natural Chromium Sequestrant

Santhiya Jayakumar and K. J. Sharmila†

Department of Biotechnology, Dr. M.G.R. Educational and Research Institute, Maduravoyal, Chennai-600095, Tamil Nadu, India

†Corresponding author: K. J. Sharmila; sharmila.ibt@drmgrdu.ac.in; orcid id: 0000-003-0685-9900
orcid id: 0009-0003-4124-3973

santhiya jayakumar orcid id:
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ABSTRACT

Industrialization is key to a nation's progress, but exposure to industrial effluents containing heavy metals can cause deadly diseases; therefore, mitigation measures must be applied to safeguard both human beings and the environment. In this study, loofah sponges, a natural heavy metal sequestrant, were modified with sodium hydroxide, acetic acid, sequestering, and wetting agents and showed increased mechanical strength with strong interfacial bonding with the composite materials than untreated loofah sponge. Characterization techniques, including ASTM-D570, FTIR, SEM, SEM-EDX, TGA (thermogravimetry analysis), XRD (X-ray diffraction spectra), and Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) were employed to investigate the SSGP-pretreated loofah sponge. The FTIR and SEM examination revealed the removal of waxes and contaminants and heavy metal adsorption on the loofah sponge noted in the SEM-EDX image. The ICP-OES analysis revealed that the pretreated loofah sponge adsorbed about 39 mg/g of chromium. This study proved that pretreated loofah sponges adsorbed about 12.4% more chromium than untreated loofah sponges. Therefore, a pretreated loofah sponge, an environmentally based green technology, can be utilized as an effective biocarrier for heavy metal-contaminated effluents. This study supports the Sustainable Development Goals of clean water and sanitation and recommends using a modified loofah sponge for large-scale applications.

INTRODUCTION

Public Health Services in different countries reported the exposure of hazardous excess metals to significant numbers of people in different ways (Cotruvo 2017). The high atomic density and weight are properties of recalcitrant heavy metals that make them quite toxic, even at low concentrations, when released into the environment. Heavy metals were released into the environment after industrialization as untreated or partially treated effluents, which were discharged into the water stream. Due to their constant and bioaccumulation properties, heavy metal sets constantly accumulate in the environment (Saxena et al. 2024, Vidhya et al. 2023). Heavy metals are naturally released into the environment through the leaching of rock and soil into water streams or by human activities, such as the discharge of untreated wastewater directly into rivers (Rezooqi et al. 2021). According to the US EPA, lead, cadmium, and chromium are designated as the top-priority contaminants of major public concern (Faheem et al. 2020). In general, heavy metals are carcinogenic and mutagenic, and they also induce cell apoptosis. Therefore, to mitigate the effects of such heavy metals, natural methods must be taken into account. The advantages and disadvantages of conventional processes are depicted in Fig. 1.

Although advantages are present in conventional processes (Agarwal et al. 2006), the disadvantages outweigh the benefits, making biosorption a glimpse of the future (Kanamarpudi et al. 2018). Naturally, chromium is predominantly

Fig. 1: Advantages and disadvantages of conventional process.

encountered in its oxidation states Cr (VI) and Cr (III) (Goddeti et al. 2020), where Cr (VI) showed several times more toxicity, as it is present in industrial effluents that are discharged in tones, so chromium mitigation must be propelled as it is carcinogenic and mutagenic. The loofah sponge (LS) is obtained from the dried fruit of *Luffa cylindrica* (L.), a member of the Cucurbitaceae family, and features a polyporous structure. When dried, it forms a natural mat that can serve as a bio-adsorbent for treating industrial effluents. Asia, Africa, and tropical America are the main cultivation spots for loofah plants (Oboh & Aluyor 2009). The LS has a higher strength, stiffness, and energy absorption capacity and contains cellulose (62%), hemicelluloses (20%), lignin (11.2%), extractives (3.2%), and ash (0.4%), with functional groups that adsorb metals from various sources. Over the past decade, LS has been explored less as a source of wastewater treatment than other fibers; therefore, this research investigated LS as a heavy metal sequestrant for wastewater treatment. This study evaluated the potential of chemically SSGP-pretreated loofah (treated with sodium hematophosphate, sodium hydroxide, glycerol, and potassium permanganate) as a heavy metal sequestrant for the treatment of industrial wastewater. Unmodified loofah adsorbed about 34.7 mg/g

of chromium, while SSGP-pretreated LS adsorbed about 39 mg/g of chromium.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fiber Collection

Dried LS in sizes between 18 and 22 cm was chosen and collected from a local market in Perambur, Chennai, Tamil Nadu. It was washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove dirt and soil, then dried and cut down to a size of 2 cm for use.

Fiber Modification Process

Washing and pre-sterilization: The 0.85% saline solution was used to remove dirt and biofilms. The loofah was then cut into 2 cm height and pretreated with chemical treatments.

Alkali treatment: To increase the tensile strength of LS, 4% NaOH was used to treat LS at 120°C for 4 hours using a hot plate stirrer. Then washed and dried in a hot air oven at 120°C.

Acid treatment: LS was treated with 2% acetic acid at room temperature for 30 min and washed with distilled water.

Fig. 2: (a) LS (b) cross-section of LS (c) cut piece of LS (d) alkaline, acid treated LS (e) KMnO₄ treated LS (f) SSGP-pretreated LS.

Neutral salt treatment: LS was treated with 0.6% potassium permanganate for 5 min at room temperature and washed thoroughly till a neutral pH was reached.

Sequestering agent: LS treated with 2 % (2 g/l) of sodium hematophosphate at 50°C for 3 hours and washed with distilled water.

Wetting agent: LS was further treated with 30% glycerol for 30 min and washed again with distilled water and 70% ethanol several times to remove dirt and scum, then dried in a hot air oven at 160°C for 4 h and used. The LS and its treatment are depicted in Fig. 2.

The fabricated LS were modified using sodium hydroxide, acetic acid, potassium permanganate (Hallad et al. 2019), and sodium hematophosphate. The inorganic cyclophosphate sodium hematophosphate increases permeability (Sampaio et al. 2022) and removes surface impurities, acting as both a surfactant and a sequestrant (Karim et al. 2024). It was used in conjunction with alkali and potassium permanganate, which enhances the strength of the fiber. The tenacity of the fibers increases, elongation of the fibers occurs (Wetaka et al. 2016), and delignification of the fibers occurs (Ghali et al. 2009), which enhances the shelf life of the fibers. Acetic acid replaces water, aiding in the plastination of fiber (Dhir et al. 2020), and shifts the pH to neutral due to alkali treatment. Glycerol decreases surface tension and reduces the propensity of molecules to stick together (Karim et al. 2024).

Physicochemical Characterization of Loofah Sponge

ASTM-D570 test: The ASTM D570 procedure is used for interpreting the adsorption rate of untreated and SSGP-pretreated LS. Approximately 10 × 0.5 × 0.1 mm LS were immersed in a separate container containing distilled water for one hour at room temperature. Samples were removed

at 15-minute intervals and kept between filter sheets under weights. LS water absorption percentages were calculated by weighing the filter paper using a digital balance machine (Tanobe et al. 2014).

$$\text{Water Absorption \%} = \frac{\text{weight after immersion} - \text{weight before immersion}}{\text{weight before immersion}} \times 100$$

FTIR: The positional status of LS chemical functional groups was ascertained by a Fourier Transform InfraRed spectrophotometer (FTIR, Shimadzu IRTRACER 100, Japan). The untreated and treated LS, each at about 1 mg, was crushed and mixed with a 200 mg dosage of potassium bromide at room temperature and 65% humidity. The interaction of infrared light with untreated and SSGP-pretreated LS produces its molecular fingerprint in the wavenumber range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ at a scan rate of 32 with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹.

XRD: The crystalline and amorphous structures of untreated and treated LS were investigated by X-ray Diffraction (XRD, X'Pert PRO MRD, PANalytical, Netherlands) at a 50 mA current and 40 kV voltage. The untreated and treated LS diffraction measurements were scanned from 5 to 100 (2θ) with a 0.9° min⁻¹ scanning rate at 25°C.

TG analysis: Thermogravimetry (TG) was performed on untreated and treated LS using a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGDTA, NETZSCH, STA 449F5, Germany) with a heating rate of 30°C/10.0°C/min to 700°C.

SEM (SEM, AMETEK): The surface morphological property of the loofah fiber was observed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, AMETEK, United States), with an imaging mode at 2 micrometers and a working distance of 20 mm. The loofah fibers were prepared using an aluminum

carrier precipitation method and then covered with a thin gold film under a high vacuum at a 15 kV voltage.

SEM EDX: The gold-sputtered loofah fibers were analyzed for their different elements to determine their strength and distribution using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) detector (EDX AMETEK BV, Tilburg, Netherlands).

ICP-OES: The samples were acid-digested and analyzed for elemental characterization using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES, Agilent Technologies).

Chromium Removal By Loofah Sponges

Approximately 1 gram of LS was added to 100 mL of 200 ppm chromium-containing conical flasks and incubated for 6 days at 120 RPM and 37°C. The filtrate was then removed, and the sample was analyzed for chromium presence using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) analysis (Agilent Technologies, USA).

RESULTS

Water Adsorption Test

The LS was cut into 10 x 0.5 x 0.1 mm and used for the adsorption test. The LS showed increased adsorption with an increase in contact time. The absorbency of untreated and SSGP-pretreated LS showed 123% and 114% adsorption within 15 min, respectively, with a further increase in adsorption noted. The highest adsorption rates were 132% and 137% for untreated and SSGP-pretreated fiber, respectively, noted within 24 hours. SSGP-pretreated LS has more water adsorption capacity than untreated LS, so it has great efficiency in absorbing the contaminated effluents that benefit the contamination removal as well as heavy metals removal.

FTIR

FTIR results indicate that sodium hematophosphate-sodium hydroxide, glycerol, and potassium permanganate treatments

Fig. 3: FTIR spectra peaks of (a) untreated, (b) SSGP-pretreated LS.

Table 1: Chemical stretches and bending distributions and peak locations of Luffa fiber.

Untreated	Treated	Chemical stretching	Reference
420	420	Aryl disulfides S-S stretch	(Coates, 1996)
430	-	C-Cl stretching vibration	(Balachandran et al. 2011)
449	447	449 cm ⁻¹ (PO ₄ bond) to aryl disulfides: S-S stretch.	(Coates, 1996; Ramdan et al. 2017)
513	-	C-H bending vibrations.	(Jeya et al. 2018)
897	897	C-O-C stretching, β-glycosidic linkage.	(Rahman & Khan 2007)
1028	1026	Pectin-OH bond stretches more in SSGP-pretreated LS than in untreated alkyl and aryl halides. In untreated loofah fibers, C-H stretches happened at higher points.	(Mollah et al. 2023)
1244	1153	C-O stretching (1244 cm ⁻¹) to C-O-C bond (1153 cm ⁻¹).	(Rusu et al. 2008; Saito & Iwata 2012)
1323	1263	NO ₂ stretches (1323 cm ⁻¹) shifts to C-H stretching at 1263 cm ⁻¹ in the fingerprint region-pyranose ring.	(Thombare et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2018)
1373	1321	Phenol O-H bending (medium) of the untreated material shifts to alkane C-H stretch (methyl and methylene groups of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin).	(Lakshmanan et al. 2018)
1636	1425	The alkene C=C symmetric stretch (medium) in untreated fibers is shifted to CH ₂ bending, which is hidden in fingerprint regions.	(Sentharamaikannan et al. 2019)
2920	1639	The alkane CH ₂ asymmetrical stretching (2920 cm ⁻¹ , medium bond) of waxes in loofah fibers shifts to the alkene C=C stretch (medium) in SSGP-pretreated fibers.	(Zhang et al. 2018)
3333	2899	The sharp alcoholic O-H stretch (med) of untreated samples shifts to the alkane C-H stretch (med, which is present in lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose methyl and methylene groups).	(Zeng et al. 2019)
3758	3333	Pectin, sharp alcoholic O-H stretching of untreated fibers (α - cellulose) shifts to sharp alcoholic O-H stretch (med stretching (lignin).	(Karim et al. 2023)

were perfectly incorporated into the fiber, and chemical modifications shifted peaks of LS from a higher wavelength

to a lower wavelength. The FTIR peaks show the chemical complexity nature of untreated LS and SSGP-pretreated

Fig. 4: (a) XRD graph interpretation; (b) XRD-SSGP-pretreated; (c) XRD-untreated LS.

Fig. 5: TGDTA analysis of untreated and treated LS.

LS, as depicted in Fig. 3. Functional groups and chemical stretching involved in pretreated and SSGP-modified LS at a wavelength between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} were shown in Table 1. The untreated sample, with bond frequencies at 430 cm^{-1} and 513 cm^{-1} , denotes highly polar covalently bonded C-Cl stretching and C-H bending vibrations, respectively, which are not present in the treated sample. The chemical modifications show an increase in bond dissociation energy with increased heat, breaking bonds to simpler forms or free bonds, which helps sequester heavy metals to LS.

XRD

Sharp and strong peaks indicate the crystallinity property of both LS samples; SSGP-pretreated LS shows increased tensile strength. The pattern of untreated loofah exhibits a broad peak at $2\theta = 21.6^\circ$ and a small peak at 21.1° , 17.9° . The pattern of SSGP-pretreated loofah exhibits a broad peak at $2\theta = 41.24^\circ$, 27.9° , and a small peak at 9.37° (Fig. 4).

The characteristic peaks at 9.3° were not present in untreated LS. The 41.27° peak shifts to 41.24° , and the 27.6° peak shifts to 27.9° with higher relative intensity. The

increase in crystallinity index shows high tensile strength and microstructural regularity of SSGP-pretreated LS. Therefore, chemical modifications in LS increased the crystalline index, resulting in modified LS that exhibits higher strength, wear resistance, and toughness, as well as ductility, compared to untreated LS.

TG/DTA

Thermogravimetric analysis was performed using a thermal analyzer (NETZSCH STA 449F5, Germany) for both

Table 2: TGDTA analysis of LS.

Temperature °C	TGDTA Untreated %	TGDTA SSGP-pretreated %
100	11.6	8.7
200	12	17.05
300	32	27.2
400	80	37.3
500	99.3	47.3
600	100	57.3
700	100	66.9

untreated and treated LS at a heating rate of 10 K/min and a nitrogen flow rate of 250 ml/min in the temperature range of 30-700°C (Matter, Hassan, Elfaramawy, & Esmail, 2024). The result shows that at temperature 700°C, only 66.9% mass loss occurred in SSGP-pretreated LS, but untreated LS mass loss happened within 600°C, showing the modification treatment by SSGP greatly strengthened SSGP-pretreated LS, and as the sturdiness is increased in SSGP-modified LS, it can be reused more than untreated LS Fig. 5, Table 2.

SEM

The morphological properties of untreated and treated fiber at 300 X magnification were captured using Scanning Electron Microscopy images (FEI Quanta 600 FEG ESEM, USA). The change in surface morphology, removal of waxes, and surface impurities on surface visualized in SEM images. The waxes and impurities on the loofah surface prevent water adsorption in untreated LS. After chemical treatment, a surface free from waxes, dirt, and impurities was visible in SEM images (Fig. 6).

SEM-EDX

SEM with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (SEM-EDX; FEI Quanta 600 FEG ESEM, USA) elemental analysis showed the presence of the Crystal lattice structured chromium heavy metal presence in the surface of both untreated and SSGP modified LS (Fig. 7). The weight and atomic percentage of up to 26.82% and 30% were noted in the surface of LS, which shows free bonds sequestered the heavy metal on the LS surface as well as layers of LS. Therefore, the modified LS demonstrates the chromium adsorption capability across all layers of LS.

ICP-OES Analysis

The ICP-OES analysis utilizes argon plasma to excite the HM-containing solution, emitting light with a wavelength proportional to the elements. The analysis showed that untreated loofah adsorbed only 34 mg/g of chromium, but SSGP-pretreated LS adsorbed about 39 mg/g of chromium, which is 12.4 % more than untreated LS. Thus,

Fig. 6: SEM images of (a) untreated; (b) SSGP-pretreated.

Fig. 7: SEM-EDX of elemental chromium.

LS modification has increased chromium adsorption at the surface and in the layers, as confirmed by the ICP-OES analysis.

DISCUSSION

The conventional treatment process is harmful to our environment as it uses chemicals in large amounts, which makes the process expensive. Additionally, conventional approaches have several disadvantages, as discussed in Fig. 1, making the secondary pollutants discharged during these treatments a significant threat to our environment. The treated water must be further treated to remove these chemicals, which makes the process unacceptable. The natural bioremediation of heavy metals is achieved through various approaches, including the use of activated carbon, biological organism-based heavy metal biodegradation, and bioremediation using natural fibers. The activated carbon-based bioremediation results showed that activated carbons from different sources exhibited varying results and demonstrated specificity in adsorption. The activated carbon process requires a significant amount of materials as its source, but only a very small amount is produced at the end of pyrolysis, which can even lead to air pollution.

The activated carbon cannot be implemented on a large scale because the source varies, and the result also varies. Additionally, pyrolyzing tons of sources daily raises significant concerns, making large-scale implementation unapproachable. The biological-based treatment is a great source of bioremediation, but growing microbes daily requires a good source of amendments, which makes the process expensive. Additionally, environmental contamination is a possibility, and the failure of the approach is also a concern. Implementing one organism is not possible, so different micro-organism-based bioremediation must be studied as the optimized heavy metal degradation is possible only at optimized conditions, which is specific for different organisms, so implementing on a large scale requires a bioreactor for propelling certain organisms at certain conditions, and using organisms that is not present in that habitat may cause an imbalance in the environment. In certain studies, genetically modified organisms are also used, so ethical reasoning is also present in this approach, so this technique has a lot of lagging in large scale implantation. The LS natural adsorbent is cost-effective, and locally available materials can be implemented as it is inexpensive. And makes this technique approachable. This technique can be combined with existing technology to make the process more cost-

Fig. 8: Chromium adsorption by natural fiber.

effective or used as a novel approach. This technique doesn't require new plant construction, as it can be implemented in any existing treatment plant, and it is also easy to train professionals for this approach. The collected samples were cut in 2 cm size and modified with SSGP. LS is composed of 55–90% of cellulose, 8–22% of hemicellulose, 10–23% lignin, extractives >3.2%, ash, and others 0.4% (Chen et al. 2019), as the impurity blocks the water adsorption, alkali treatment is done (Begum et al. 2021). The SSGP-pretreated LS exhibited approximately 137% increased water adsorption with an increase in contact time (Tanobe et al. 2014). FT-IR spectra peaks at a wavelength between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} in untreated and SSGP-pretreated LS show a change in functional groups, and certain wavenumbers were not present in modified LS, which shows incorporation of SSGP, lower bond energy, and also change in chemical stretching is also noted in modified LS as mentioned in Fig. 3, Table 1. An increase in tensile strength and crystallinity index was noted, with sharp and strong peaks in modified LS (Mohanta & Acharya 2016). Additionally, more peaks, such as $2\theta = 9.37^\circ$, demonstrated the robustness of the modified LS (Goddeti et al. 2020). The thermogravimetric analysis of both LS and the SSGP-modified LS shows that they withstand approximately 40% of the sample, even at 700°C (Matter et al. 2024). The SSGP-pretreated LS exhibited a clear surface morphology, with water adsorption impeding the presence of waxes and impurities (Goddeti et al. 2020, Matter et al. 2024). Additionally, chromium metal was noted on the LS surface (Mohanta & Acharya 2016). The ICP-OES analysis (Kotelnikova et al. 2024, Zeng et al. 2019) proved the adsorption status of LS, SSGP-modified

LS about adsorbed 39 mg/g of chromium, which is more than previously reported studies with sugarcane bagasse (Sharma & Forster 1994), banana fiber (Begum et al. 2020), agave bagasse (Bernardo et al. 2009), coconut fiber (Franguelli et al. 2019), peat and coconut fiber (Kaszycki et al. 2004) and more depicted in Fig. 8.

The modified LS was reported to be copper sequestrant in our previous study (Jayakumar & Sharmila 2024). This study recommends the environmentally based green technology of using SSGP-pretreated LS as a superior option for chromium sequestration, which can be applied in large-scale applications. Thus, the SSGP-pretreated LS can be utilized as a source of heavy metal sequestration in industrial effluents contaminated by chromium and can also be employed at metal-contaminated sites for enhanced chromium sequestration.

Potential Challenges of Large-Scale Application

Although using LS for secondary treatment can be a novel approach or combined with conventional methods, approving new technology by the public, as well as government and private bodies, takes considerable time.

LS is seasonal and requires a significant amount of time to grow and harvest, so fibers must be switched or stocked for future use.

Future Research

In the future, the SSGP treatment must be tested for other fibers, as per the local availability of India as well as other

countries, for converting the conventional approach, which produces the secondary pollutants as the result of treatment, to a natural fiber-based green approach for the betterment of one's country's agriculture sector as well as reducing contamination in the environment using agriculture based natural fibers such as LS. The SSGP-LS was tested only for copper and chromium sequestration; therefore, further research is needed to investigate the removal of other heavy metals and pollutants, such as dyes, as well as contaminants like sulfate, nitrate, total dissolved solids, and total suspended solids.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that novel SSGP-pretreated LS is an effective adsorbent for heavy metals. The sodium hemetaphosphate, glycerol, potassium permanganate, acetic acid, sodium hydroxide modified, and SSGP-pretreated LS showed effective chromium adsorption; about a 12.4% increase in efficiency of chromium adsorption was noted. The FTIR results proved the successful incorporation of SSGP in pretreated LS, and XRD results showed SSGP-pretreated LS is more crystalline and sturdier than untreated LS. SEM images showed that the chemical treatments significantly removed the impurities and waxes present in LS, which prevents water adsorption. The SEM-EDX results showed the efficiency of untreated and SSGP-pretreated LS as chromium adsorbent; the crystalline lattice structure of chromium was observed in LS. The ICP-OES analysis proved the chromium adsorption capacity of SSGP-pretreated LS, with a 12.4% further increase in adsorption noted. The SSGP-pretreated adsorbent exhibits good chromium adsorption, approximately 39 mg.g⁻¹, making it suitable for use as a heavy metal sequestrant in heavy metal-contaminated industrial discharges and sites that receive sludge with heavy metals. So, the SSGP-modified LS can be used as a strong metals sequestrant. This study utilized simulated heavy metals for treatment; therefore, future research should test real-time tannery effluent to observe the SSGP-LS efficiency in sequestering metals, as well as other contaminants.

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